

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part V. Sorption of Ethanol and Methanol Vapours

BALWANT RAI PURI & R. C. MALIK

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-14

Received 30 August 1971

Sorption isotherms of methanol and ethanol on caseins were determined, using a quartz spring balance technique, at 40°. The isotherms permit the application of B.E.T. as well as Harkins and Jura equations. The methanol areas of caseins, as obtained from B.E.T. plots, are in good agreement with the corresponding values reported earlier from water isotherms. The ethanol areas, however, are somewhat lower. The value of k of Harkins and Jura equation for methanol has been shown to be about 3.67 whereas the value for water, reported in the literature, is 3.86. The heats of adsorption as well as free energy changes involved, as calculated from the respective isotherms, decrease in the order; water > methanol > ethanol. The V_m value of methanol and ethanol corresponds to coverage of about 1.5 and 3 ionic sites, per molecule, respectively, as compared to the corresponding value of 1 for water vapour. The results indicate parallel orientation of the adsorbates along casein surface.

The perusal of the literature shows that while a number of studies on sorption of water vapour by a variety of proteins¹⁻¹³, including a few on caseins^{6,10,11}, have been reported, little work has been done on the sorption of methanol, ethanol or other polar organic vapours by these materials. The importance of water sorption, as a possible tool for the estimation of surface area of proteins and in indicating possible interaction of polar water molecules with ionic groups in proteins has been rightly emphasised^{3,4,6,7}. It would be of interest to know how the presence of hydrocarbon chain of increasing length in the alcohol molecules alters the sorptive behaviour of caseins. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials · Two samples of casein, one from cow's milk and the other from buffalos' milk, were prepared by each one of the following methods ·

- (a) Hammarsten method (precipitation by acetic acid at pH 4.6)
- (b) Zoller method (precipitation by HCl-citric acid mixture at pH 4.6)
- (c) Van Slyke-Bosworth method (precipitation as in (a) above, dissolving in ammonia, precipitating out calcium on the addition of ammonium oxalate and re-precipitation at pH 4.6 on the addition of HCl)
- (d) Rennet method.

The details of these methods were described earlier¹⁴. Thus 8 samples in all, 4 from cows' and 4 from buffalos' milk, were prepared. Methanol used was of B.D.H., A.R. quality while ethanol was obtained by distilling rectified spirit repeatedly over lime and finally over sodium.

Vapour sorption isotherms: Sorption isotherms (40°) were determined by using a modified McBain's balance with quartz fibre spring. The equilibrium at each relative vapour pressure was obtained, generally, between 2 and 2½ hr. Three hours exposure, therefore, was allowed in every case. The sorption values when calculated in terms of g/100 g were fairly reproducible within ±0.1 of one another.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The methanol and ethanol sorption isotherms (40°) on the caseins isolated from cows' milk by the various methods are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. The isotherms on the buffalos' caseins were similar except for the fact that the sorption values were slightly lower. These have not been plotted for reasons of space. The sorption of methanol as well as ethanol on Van Slyke-Bosworth casein is seen to be relatively more than that on the other varieties. It appears that the removal of calcium from the caseinate complex, as is done in this method, makes more sites available for the sorption of methanol as well as ethanol vapours. The remaining three varieties do not show significant differences.

Fig. 1. Methanol vapour sorption isotherms of cows' caseins.

All the isotherms belong to type II of the well known classification of adsorption isotherms, indicating formation of multimolecular layers. It was thought of interest, therefore, to analyse the data first by the BET equation, viz.,

$$\frac{X}{(1-X)V} = \frac{1}{V_m \cdot C} + \frac{C-1}{V_m \cdot C} X$$

where V is the weight of the vapour sorbed per unit weight of the adsorbent at relative vapour pressure X (i.e., p/p_0), V_m is the weight of the vapour required to form a monomolecular layer and C is a constant related to heat of adsorption and given by the expression

$$C = e^{E_1 - E_l/RT}$$

where E_1 is the heat of adsorption in the first layer and E_l the heat of liquefaction of the adsorbate.

Fig. 2. Ethanol vapour sorption isotherms of buffalos' caseins.

The plots of $X/V(1-X)$ against X give reasonably straight lines upto 0.4 r.v.p. (cf. Figs. 3 and 4), as expected. The slopes of these lines and the intercepts on the ordinate give $C-1/V_m.C$ and $1/V_m.C$, respectively, from which the values of V_m and $E_1 - E_l$ can be calculated. Knowing the molecular areas of methanol and ethanol to be 16.7 and 25.1 Å².

Fig. 3. BET plots of methanol sorption isotherms on cows' caseins.

respectively, specific surface areas of caseins were calculated from the values of V_m . Further, knowing the values of E_1 for methanol and ethanol at 40° to be 8.717 and 9.890 Kcal/mole,

Fig. 4. BET plots of ethanol sorption isotherms on buffalos' caseins.

the values of E_1 for both the adsorbates were also calculated. These results are given in Table 1. The corresponding values of specific surface area and E_1 , obtained from the water isotherms¹¹, are also reproduced for the sake of ready reference in the parentheses.

It is seen that while the methanol areas are in fair agreement with the areas obtained from water isotherms, the ethanol areas are relatively low. The values of E_1 for water, methanol and ethanol are of the same order showing that interacting forces are of the same kind. However, they decrease as we move from water to methanol and then to ethanol.

The free energy change accompanying the sorption of one g. of methanol and ethanol vapours by casein which may be regarded as a quantitative measure of the affinity of the adsorbent for the vapour may be calculated by using the equation

$$\Delta F = \frac{RT}{M} \int_0^1 a \frac{dX}{X}$$

where M is the molecular weight of the adsorbate and 'a' is the weight of the vapour adsorbed on 1 g. of dry casein. The integration was carried out by plotting a/X against X and multiplying the area under the curve by RT/M , as was done earlier¹¹ in the case of sorption of water vapour. The values of ΔF for methanol and ethanol on the various samples of casein, included in Table 1, are seen to be appreciably lower than those obtained earlier for water and reproduced in the parentheses. This is, again, indicative of weaker interactions of methanol and ethanol than that of water with caseins.

The isotherms were also analysed by using Harkins and Jura equation, viz.,

$$\log X = B - A/V^2$$

TABLE 1

Specific surface areas and heats and free energy changes of sorption of water, methanol and ethanol vapours

Description of the sample	Specific surface area from		Ethanol sorption isotherms		Heats of sorption in the first layer		Free energy of sorption for	
	Methanol (& water) sorption isotherms	S.S.A. (m ² /g)	V _m (mg/g)	S.S.A. (m ² /g)	Methanol (& water) (K cal/mole)	Ethanol (K cal/mole)	Methanol (& water)	Ethanol
<i>Cows' Caseins</i>								
Rennet	54.4 (53.0)*	177 (187)	39.0	127	11.696 (12.175)	10.130	-402 (-822)	-200
Hammarsten	53.9 (50.7)	175 (178)	41.1	135	11.750 (12.946)	10.467	-404 (-790)	-209
Zoller	52.4 (50.1)	170 (176)	40.0	130	11.880 (13.200)	10.217	-408 (-844)	-196
Vanslyke-Bosworth	57.5 (47.6)	187 (169)	40.5	132	11.924 (12.978)	10.527	-445 (-775)	-239
<i>Buffalos' Caseins</i>								
Rennet	53.4 (51.3)	173 (180)	31.2	102	11.336 (12.305)	10.181	-384 (-542)	-188
Hammarsten	53.0 (45.6)	171 (180)	39.7	129	11.338 (12.343)	10.184	-406 (-705)	-195
Zoller	50.7 (43.3)	164 (152)	37.6	121	11.540 (13.290)	10.042	-365 (-744)	-180
Vanslyke-Bosworth	54.3 (45.6)	177 (162)	38.0	123	11.221 (12.343)	10.157	-412 (-717)	-213

* The values given in the parantheses relate to sorption of water vapour.

where A and B are constants. The plots of $\log X$ against $1/V^2$ for the various caseins are seen to be linear in the case of methanol as well as ethanol (cf. Figs. 5 and 6) upto a considerable range of vapour pressure. The results thus permit the application of Harkins

Fig. 5. Harkins and Jura plots of methanol sorption isotherms on cows' caseins.

and Jura equation as well. These authors suggest the calculation of specific surface area (S.S.) by the relationship

$$\text{S.S.} = kA^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

where A is the slope of the linear plot and k is a constant depending upon the nature of the adsorbate, the value being, for example, 4.06 for nitrogen and 3.83 for water. The value for alcohols has not been reported. However, by substituting the specific surface areas, as obtained from the B.E.T. treatment, and the slopes shown in Figs. 5 and 6, the values of k for methanol were obtained. These are given in Table 2 and are seen to be quite close to one another in the case of all the caseins. Thus an average value of 3.67 can be taken for methanol. This value, incidentally, is fairly close to that for water and shows, again, that the nature of the interaction is the same in both cases and that the difference is of degree and not of kind.

TABLE 2

Calculation of k of Harkins Jura equation for methanol

	Specific surface area (m ² /g)	\sqrt{A}	k
<i>Cows caseins</i>			
Rennet	177	4.77	3.69
Hammarsten	175	4.71	3.67
Zoller	170	4.58	3.71
Vanslyke-Bosworth	187	5.10	3.67
<i>Buffalos' caseins</i>			
Rennet	173	4.66	3.71
Hammarsten	171	4.70	3.64
Zoller	164	4.50	3.62
Vanslyke-Bosworth	171	4.82	3.67

Some workers^{10,13} have questioned the application of B.E.T. equation to the sorption of water vapour (and, may be, by implication, to the sorption of alcohol vapour as well) on proteins in general. Bull and Breese¹³ ignoring the equation, calculated the number

Fig. 6. Harkins and Jura plots of ethanol sorption isotherms on cows' caseins.

of hydrophilic polar groups from the amount of water adsorbed at a relative humidity of 0.92. The values agreed with those obtained from the amino acid contents of the proteins. They concluded that nearly 6 molecules of water are adsorbed per polar group at this relative vapour pressure (r.v.p.) which, obviously, is quite close to the saturation vapour pressure. Pauling¹⁵, however, using B.E.T. constant, V_m , the amount of water required to form a mono layer, completed at a much lower r.v.p., concluded that one molecule of water is bound by one molecule of hydrophilic amino acid residue in the case of a number of proteins examined by him. We have also shown in the study of water isotherms on casein¹¹ that V_m is obtained at 0.18 r.v.p. and the amount corresponds to the sorption of one molecule of water per polar group. It was thought of interest to know if a similar situation holds in the case of sorption of methanol and ethanol as well. The number of ionic groups in the three acid caseins, is obtained from their titration curves¹⁴. The number of methanol and ethanol molecules corresponding to the respective V_m values are also included in separate columns. It appears from the data that one methanol molecule covers roughly 1.5 ionic sites while one ethanol molecule covers roughly 3 such sites. The reason for the higher values lies, probably, in the molecular areas of water, methanol and ethanol. It is highly likely that the non polar hydrocarbon chain, which is even larger in ethanol than in methanol, blocks access to some of the neighbouring ionic groups and thus renders them inaccessible for interaction with polar OH groups of the alcohol molecules. It is interesting to note in this connection that molecular areas of methanol (16.7 \AA^2) and ethanol (25.1 \AA^2) are about 1.5 and 2.5 times larger, respectively, than molecular area of water (10.5 \AA^2). These observations are also significant in showing that the adsorbate molecules are oriented parallel to the surface and support the findings of Kipling¹⁶ for orientation of alcohols on polar surfaces.

Harte and Rupley¹⁷ as well as Bull and Breese¹³ have shown that nearly 50% of an exposed protein surface is hydrophobic. If there was any interaction between the hydrophobic surface of the protein and hydrophobic part of methanol or ethanol molecule, then the sorption of methanol and ethanol would have been much more than that of water. That, however, is not the case.

It may be noted that although V_m for methanol corresponds to less than one molecule per ionic group, unlike that in water, and the interaction is also weaker, yet the specific surface areas, as obtained from methanol isotherms, are fairly close to those obtained from water isotherms. It appears that even though some of the ionic groups get covered by the hydrocarbon part of the methanol molecule and thus become inaccessible for the interaction, the larger area of the methanol molecule provides the necessary compensation.

The methanol as well as ethanol isotherms (Figs. 1 and 2) can be split into three segments. The first segment ends at a value close to V_m at a relative vapour pressure lying in the range 0.2–0.24. The progress of the sorption with further increase in r.v.p. slows down, thereafter, till a value close to $2V_m$ is obtained at a r.v.p. around 0.6 (in the range 0.58–0.63). It appears that in this region the non-ionic polar groups, the number of which, incidentally, is quite close to that of the ionic groups, are becoming increasingly accessible to polar groups of methanol and ethanol at gradually increasing r.v.p.'s. Beyond that begins the third segment in which each isotherm tends to assume an upward swing indicating formation of

subsequent layers. It can be shown that the thickness of the adsorbed layer near the saturation vapour pressure corresponds roughly to 4-5 statistical layers in the case of both methanol and ethanol. It is not unlikely that in the region of high vapour pressures methanol and ethanol vapours are also taken up at the peptide bond.

One of us (R.C.M.) is thankful to the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, Krishi Bhawan, New Delhi for financial assistance.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. D. D. Eley and R. B. Lesile, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1966, **62**, 1002.
2. Jerrold, M. Seehof, Bertram Keilin and Sidney W. Benson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2427.
3. A. D. McLaren and John W. Rowen, *J. Polymer Sci.*, 1951, **7**, 289.
4. H. B. Bull, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **66**, 1499.
5. Edward F. Mellon, Alfred H. Korn, Elsie L. Kokes and Sam R. Hoover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1870.
6. R. W. Green, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, (New Zealand), 1949, **77**, 313.
7. E. F. Mellon, A. H. Korn and S. R. Hoover, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3040.
8. O. L. Sponsler, J. D. Bath and J. W. Ellis, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1940, **44**, 996.
9. H. J. Frey and W. J. Moore, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3644.
10. E. Berlin, B. A. Anderson and M. J. Pallansch, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, **73**, 303.
11. B. R. Puri, K. K. Toteja and R. C. Malik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 554.
12. T. M. Shaw, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1944, **12**, 391.
13. H. B. Bull and K. Breese, *Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1968, **128**, 488.
14. B. R. Puri, K. K. Toteja and R. C. Malik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 889.
15. L. Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 555.
16. J. J. Kipling, "Adsorption from Solutions of Non-electrolytes". Academic Press, New York, 1965.
17. R. A. Harte and J. A. Rupley, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1968, **243**, 1663.